

VAUGHAN'S PIER WATERBRD SURVEY: METADATA FOR DATA TABLES

Filename	Contents	Field	Data type	Details
VP_2020_21_count_data.csv	Waterbird count data	Date	Date	Count date
		Count	Text	EB = ebb tide count LT = low tide count FL = flood tide count Sequential numbers are used to differentiate between separate counts on the same date: e.g., EB1, EB2, EB3, EB4, EB5
		Distance	Text	Distance band: 0 = 0-50 m 50 = 50-100 m 100 = 100-200 m 200 = 200-300 m 300 = > 300 m
		Zone	Text	INT = intertidal SUB = subtidal SUP = supratidal TERR = terrestrial TAQU = terrestrial (aquatic) See Lewis and Tierney (2014) for definitions
		Species	Text	BTO species code
		Number	Integer	Species count
		Behaviour	Text	F = feeding R = roosting H = flushed Y1 = flying (included in count totals) Y2 = flying (not included in count totals)
		Quality	Text	Count quality: OK or LOW
		DC_count	Text	Overall count double-count: YES or NO
		DC_distance band	Text	Distance band double-count: YES or NO
		Notes	Text	Free-form field for any additional notes: e.g., location details, movements, behaviour, etc.

Filename	Contents	Field	Data type	Details
VP_2020_count_details.csv	Waterbird count timings and conditions	Date	Date	Count date
		Count	Text	EB = ebb tide count LT = low tide count FL = flood tide count Sequential numbers are used to differentiate between separate counts on the same date:e.g., EB1, EB2, EB3, EB4, EB5 Note, on some of the complete counts of Whitegate Bay, there are separate entries in this table to record the count timings separately for the portions of the counts in the close and distant distance bands
		Distance	Text	Distance bands covered by count
		Time start	Time	Start time of count
		Time start	Time	End time of count
		Cloud	Integer	Cloud cover during count: 1 = 0-33% 2 = 34-66% 3 = 67-100%
		Rain	Integer	Rainfall during count: 1 = no rain 2= light showers/drizzle 3 = heavy shows/rain 4 = heavy rain
		Wind direction	Text	Compass bearing
		Wind speed	Integer	Beaufort scale
		Visibility	Integer	Visibility during count: 1 = good 2 = moderate 3 = poor 4 = very poor
		Waterbirds	Text	YES = waterbirds recorded NO = no waterbirds recorded
		Notes	Text	Free-form field for any relevant additional details: e.g., further details when reduced visibility was recorded

Filename	Contents	Field	Data type	Details
VP_2020_ disturbance_ observations.csv	Disturbance sensitivity observations	Date	Date	Observation date
		Time	Time	Observation time
		Position	Text	Reference code for position of observer, for cross-referencing with VP_2020_disturbance_positions.csv for grid references
		Ref	Integer	Unique reference number for observations made on the same day, for cross-referencing with VP_2020_disturbance_observations.csv
		Species	Text	BTO species code
		Number	Integer	Number of birds
		Behaviour	Text	F = feeding R = roosting
		Bearing	Integer	Compass bearing from the observer to the position of the bird; not corrected for grid declination
		Distance	Integer	Straight-line distance in metres from the observer to the position of the bird
		Notes	Text	Free-form field for any relevant additional details
VP_2020_ disturbance_ positions.csv	Observer positions	Position	Text	Reference code for position of observer, for cross-referencing with VP_2020_disturbance_observations.csv for grid references
		x	Integer	Irish National Grid grid reference (easting)
		y	Integer	Irish National Grid grid reference (northing)
VP_2020_ disturbance_ responses.csv	Disturbance responses recorded during the disturbance sensitivity observations	Date	Date	Observation date
		Ref	Integer	Unique reference number for observations made on the same day, for cross-referencing with VP_2020_disturbance_responses.csv
		Species	Text	BTO species code
		Response	Text	FL = flush SWIM = swam away WALK = walked away OTHER = other response, described in notes
		Move_ duration	Integer	Duration of movement response in seconds; NR = not recorded
		Resume_ duration	Integer	Total duration (including the movement duration) until bird resumed feeding after responding to the disturbance; NA = not applicable (bird was not feeding before the disturbance); NR = not recorded
		Bearing_ new	Integer	Compass bearing from the observer to the new position of the bird, after it had completed its disturbance response; not corrected for grid declination

Filename	Contents	Field	Data type	Details
VP_2021_disturbance_responses.csv	Disturbance responses recorded during the disturbance sensitivity observations	Distance_new	Integer	Straight-line distance in metres from the observer to the new position of the bird, after it had completed its disturbance response
		Notes	Text	Free-form field for any relevant additional details
VP_2021_tideline_data.csv	Tideline positions	Date	Date	Observation date
		Time	Time	Observation time
		LT_time	Time	Predicted time of low tide at Cobh from Admiralty tide tables
		Tideline	Integer	Distance in metres of the tideline from the shoreline at Vaughan's Pier

VAUGHAN'S PIER WATERBIRD SURVEY: METADATA FOR GIS DATASETS

Filename	Contents	Field	Data type	Details
VP_2021_distance_bands_polygon.shp	Distance bands from Vaughan's Pier	Band	Text	0-50 m 50-100 m 100-200 m 200-300 m > 300 m
VP_2021_tidal_exposure.shp	Intertidal habitat exposed	Distance	Integer	Distance of the tideline in metres from the shoreline at Vaughan's Pier

REFERENCE

Lewis, L.J. & Tierney, T.D. (2014). Low Tide Waterbird Surveys: Survey Methods and Guidance Notes. Irish Wildlife Manuals, No. 80. National Parks and Wildlife Service, Department of Arts, Heritage and the Gaeltacht, Ireland.